

Photolysis of 2,2''-bis (diazo) 2',2'''-biacetophenone

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Photolysis of aromatic bis-diazoketones has not so far been reported. The present note describes studies on the photolysis of 2,2''-bis(diazo) 2',2'''-biacetophenone in dry methanol and isopropanol.

Recrystallized 2,2''-bis(diazo)2',2'''-biacetophenone¹ (I), m.p. 129–130° (5g.) was dissolved in a mixture of dry dioxane (50 ml.) and dry methanol (200 ml.) in a quartz test tube fitted with a reflux condenser and exposed to two medium pressure u.v. (Hg) lamps (15 hr.). The solvents were then removed and the reaction mixture was chromatographed over alumina. Elution with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) yielded a viscous oil (2.1 g., 45%) which was found to be dimethyl 2,2'-biphenyldiacetate (II). This viscous oil on hydrolysis gave 2,2'-biphenyldiacetic acid², m.p. 152–153°. Elution with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) furnished a lactone (III), m.p. 249–250°; ν_{max}^{Nujol} 1755 cm⁻¹ (1.3 g., 32%). The mass spectrum of the lactone showed the molecular ion at m/e 234 (Found : C, 81.83%; H, 4.26%; C₁₆H₁₀O₂ requires C, 82.05% ; H, 4.27%).

The photolysis of 2,2''-bis(diazo)2',2'''-biacetophenone (5 g.) in a mixture of dry dioxane (50 ml.) and dry isopropanol (200 ml.) yielded diisopropyl 2,2'-biphenyldiacetate, m.p. 61–62° (2.5 g., 41%) and a lactone, m.p. 249–250°; ν_{max}^{Nujol} 1755 cm⁻¹ (1.7 g., 42%). The $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated lactones obtained by photolysis in methanol and isopropanol were found to be identical. There was no depression in mixed melting point. The lactone was soluble in aqueous sodium hydroxide and potassium hydroxide solutions on warming. The lactone was refluxed with aqueous potassium hydroxide (10%, 10 hr.) and then acidified with hydrochloric acid. The original lactone was obtained back. It was insoluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate.

The photolysis of a diazoketone in methanol³ produces the ester of the higher homologue of the corresponding acid and in isopropanol^{4,5} furnishes a photoreduced product along with the ester of the homologous acid. It is interesting to note that the photolysis of 2,2''-bis(diazo)2',2'''-biacetophenone in isopropanol has not produced the photoreduced product 2,2'-biacetophenone. Instead, a lactone has been obtained.

Previous authors^{3,4,5} have not obtained any lactone in photolysis of diazoketones in presence of any alcohol. Lactones have, however, been obtained by photolysis^{3,6} of monodiazoketones in inert solvents like ether, dioxane and tetrahydrofuran in absence of any hydroxylic solvent. The lactones are formed by intermolecular condensation⁶ between the diazoketone and the ketene formed during photolysis. In our experiments on the

photolysis of the bis-diazoketone in methanol and isopropanol, a lactone has been obtained in fairly good yield. This has been possible as the two diazoketo groups in 2,2''-bis(diazo) 2',2'''-biacetophenone are in favourable positions to form a lactone (III) by intramolecular condensation in the following manner.

Lactone formation by intramolecular condensation during photolysis of diazoketones has not been reported previously.

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